

PREPSOIL – Preparing the ground for healthy soils: building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge

Reference document
Conceptual framework situating the role of living labs to improve soil health

Document	4.1
Work Package and task	WP4 task 4.1
Document type	Reference paper
Dissemination level	PREPSOIL consortium before Public
Leader	INRAE
Date 1st draft	27 Feb 2023
Date finalisation	October 2023
Version	Final version
Contact	Muriel Mambrini-Doudet (muriel.mambrini@ird.fr) & Bastian Gödel

History of changes

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
V1	February 2023	Mambrini-Doudet & Goldel	Prepsoil partners task 4.1
V2	May 2023	Mambrini-Doudet & Goldel	Prepsoil partners task 4.1
V3	October 2023	Mambrini-Doudet & Goldel	1 st integration of the outcomes from the workshops
V4	November 2023	Mambrini-Doudet & Goldel	Final integration of the outcomes of the workshops after additional literature review

Disclaimer

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Abstract

The conceptual framework for using the living lab approach to improve soil health according to the 8 objectives defined by the “Mission A Soil Deal for Europe” comprises:

- A model of change outlining the activities to improve soil health and the way to implement them that will accelerate the changes, effective for every soil use
- A map setting the unique and expected features of living labs designed to improve soil health, whatever is the use of soil (generic features)
- 3 tables specifying the specific features of living labs for improving soil health in i) the agroecosystems, ii) urban areas, iii) industrial surroundings/brown fields
- An ideation to anticipate the feature of living labs for soil health in natural areas
- A reflection regarding living labs in forest areas, considered as “mixed”, combining, according to their specific situation, the features from the agroecosystems, natural areas, urban and industrial living labs.

The method to co-design the conceptual framework comprised 4 steps

- The drafting of the model for change and generic features of living labs based on the outcomes of former European projects (CSAs) aiming at setting the scene for improving European soil health, in general, for developing LL for the agroecological transition or improving urban resilience, completed by literature analysis
- The 1st proximal revision of the by the contributors to the task and the identification of expertise lacking to improve the precision of the framework thanks to regular monthly meetings
- The 1st proximal iteration with the members of the consortium, thanks to 2 successive workshops of collective intelligence.
- The 2nd iteration with experts not included or sufficiently represented in the consortium, thanks to a workshop of collective intelligence.

The outcomes are: the conceptual framework synthesised in 6 maps [1 model of change, 1 generic features of LL for soil health, 4 specific features for agroecosystems-urban-industrial-natural areas LL for soil health], background to consider Forest LL for soil health as approaches mixing the specific features of LL for the 4 different land uses, and a kit to implement workshops aiming at collective design for improving soil health.

1. Objectives

The objective is to specify the features of the Living Labs (LLs) that are and will efficiently improve soil health according to the eight challenges outlined by the Mission "A soil deal for Europe".

It is a significant step towards improving the understanding of how LLs and Lighthouses (LHs) can lead to a significant improvement of soil health. The intent is to provide the taxonomy that will support the mapping of current and emerging LLs and levers to engage LLs in their development (Task 4.2). Such an inference should also provide the framework to co-design the spectrum of model business plans (Task 4.3) considering the high variability among LLs, the diversity of land use and of the European situation regarding soil health. More generally, the framework should also support the accuracy of the service package for knowledge transfer and co-creation for LLs, prioritising specific soil needs that are foreseen in Task 4.4. More generally, it should support sharing a common background, firstly among the partners of the consortium and then with the LLs and LHs significantly engaged to improve soil health in every European member state.

2. Methods

The knowledge maps that were successively built are:

a) the generic model of change:

- the orientations of the activities that will adequately support the improvement of soil health according to the eight objectives selected by the Soil Mission
- the values that will support the engagement of the actors to engage the transition.

b) the generic features of LL significantly contributing to soil health improvements based on the model of change knowing the activities generally developed in LL

c) the unique features of LL for soil health for five land use types [agriculture, urban soils, (post-)industrial sites, natural areas and forests], by merging the characteristics of LL already existing and described in each socio-economic sector (agroecosystems, cities, industries/ brownfields and natural areas) to support the open innovation processes in each, and their refinement to accelerate the expected transitions. Regarding forest, they were considered as mixed land use (from production to natural areas, an invitation to combine the unique features of LL for each type of land use on purpose).

The steps were as such:

The drafts were initially provided by the lead INRAE based on the integration of the work undertaken in the different Coordinated Support Actions (CSAs) aiming at situating the potential of LL for improving soil health (SMS), or the agroecology transition (ALL-Ready; AE4EU), recent insights from ongoing European and Canadian LLs and completed, when needed by literature analysis. The partners of the 4.1 Task were then invited by the lead, during monthly meetings, to check collaboratively the variables of the generic model, refine the actions to be undertaken and the conditions of implementations, discuss the foreseen attributes of LLs per land use. After the checking was completed, it was time to open the drafts to additional and complementary expertise. The partners of the 4.1 Task were invited by their lead to co-design a workshop aiming at sharing the conceptual framework to invite experts and diversity of stakeholders for critical assessment and additional refinement. After having set the frame and material for a 2-hours remote working session, three successive workshops were settled, two within the PREPSOIL consortium, one with of complementary expertise (industrial and brownfield lands). The workshops were

The initial generic model of change and characteristics of LL per land use were drafted merging the results of the All-Ready (Mambrini et al., 2022), and the SMS (Maring et al., 2022) projects, completed with literature analysis and workshops. The actions and recommendations were categorised according to two plans: the activities and their implementation conditions that will lead to a significant acceleration of the sustainable transition. This map makes it easy to embrace the variables of the generic model of change. This later was used to infer the features of LL for each land use, on other words, the generic attributes of LL for soil health, categorised in terms of specific aim, activities, participants and context. Some LL are already in place or developed for specific land use in Europe and abroad, that are foreseen to have an interesting impact on soil health, and for which references are available (scientific or grey literature): LL for the agroecology transition in the agroecosystem and forestry sectors, LL to improve resilience in the urban areas, LL for the social and environmental responsibilities of the industries. The results of such LL published in the academic or grey literature or shared through workshops or interviews were checked and branched on the generic model of LL for soil health to infer the features of LL for soil health per land use. This later were thus categorised, in terms of specific aim, activities, participants and context. In doing so, we prepared the floor for the networking of LL whatever are their domain of application, and their interconnectedness at the landscape, European or international levels. Regarding natural areas and forests LL, we had to develop a specific strategy

to specify their expected features. In natural areas, we hardly find living labs. Their day-to-day management relies on multi-actor concertation, and the development, of open-innovation arrangements for specific purpose with a co-design process, might not be an easy option. To identify the expected features of LL for natural areas, we opted for collective creativity sessions on what the LL could positively add towards soil health objectives. Regarding forests, we had to reconsider our initial assumption. In first instance, we combined LL for soil health in forest with LL for soil health in the agroecosystems, because we hardly found features specific to the later that would not be find in the former. However, through the iterative working sessions, after the two workshops and a specific working session settled with the experts in Forest of Prepsol, the best way to specify the features of LL for soil health in forest is to consider that they are mix of land uses between agroecosystems, natural areas, industrial and urban environments.

Three 2-hours workshops were implemented, two with the members of PREPSOIL consortium, and one with stakeholders with complementary expertise (urban and industrial land use). Beside checking the completeness of the features that can be expected for each land use, the objective was to facilitate the share of the conceptual framework by the members of the consortium, as a precision of the common vision. In short, the participants were invited to discuss the small groups all the features, check and add eventually, missing ones, and then to co-design the expected features of LL for natural areas. Method and material are made available as a “kit” to be used by the members of the consortium or other leaders to share the conceptual framework as a common vision under which engaging their stakeholders.

Additionally, the driving forces identified can serve to evaluate or build policy incentives for the future and become powerful tools for policy-makers to revise existing regulations and to strengthen the transition process while safeguarding the public interest. Meaning, the principles and activities listed below should give frames for future actions through co-creation. In detail, we have identified the main pillars and common goods orienting the recommendations for developing activities to sustain healthy soils. they are pillars and reasons for building a balance of public, private and common goods under the perspective of reaching the goals for healthy soil. In the tables below, we grouped, on the left hand side, the main principles and context for healthy soils and on the right hand side, categories of actions that support the transition to healthy soils, generically and specifically in agricultural, urban, industrial and natural areas.

3. Results

1. Pillars of the improvement of soil health and their underpinning activities

The results are summarised in two tables and one figure.

Firstly, we outlined the driving forces of the transitions in general and specified those which will have a significant impact for soil health. They are translated in Table 1 in terms of what should be incentivized and what principle should orient the actions.

In more detail, regarding the model of change, we departed from the results of the All-Ready project (Mambrini et al., 2022), in which the activities and values that are relevant for accelerating the transition were mapped based on merging the recommendations for the agroecological transitions published by a broad range of organisations, research institutes, as well as statements and review papers. The CSA SMS (Maring et al., 2022) also developed and published similar outputs for improving soil health. The activities and values essential to the improvement of soil health were added to the map when additional. We ended with a mind map outlining the diverse categories of activities that can be implemented to improve soil health and the conditions for efficient implementation. Such map helps encompass the diversity of activities that accelerate changes, the features of the context for their successful implementation, and the specific orientations of the innovations and evolution of practice that are expected for improving soil health. Such orientations can be seen as the initial driving forces moving the communities and the various stakeholders in the transition process towards healthy soils. The activities should evolve over time, while the orientations of the changes remain.

Table 1: Fundamental pillars to secure the sustainable transition in different economic sectors and the special attention to be addressed for soil health (in brown)

To incentivise	To check regarding the action
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regeneration of ecosystems and ecosystem services Land and natural resource governance Care of nature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve biodiversity preservation Mitigate climate change Concerns for soil, water and land preservations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equity and social well-being of rural/urban/worker/citizen livelihoods Synergy among activities Fairness Social values associated to soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guarantee collective right, participation and access to the commons Insure inclusion and consideration of diversity Strengthen local empowerment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creation of knowledge and participation Creativity Connectivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote the diversity of knowledge Clarify and ensure data access and openness

The changes of practices have been gathered in five categories, which are not exclusive of each other:

- Develop synergies: enhancing key functions across diversified production systems that use the complementarities between the elements of the system.
- Seek for efficiency: producing more using fewer external resources, manage the resources for reduced input, substitute with alternate systems and practices, and opt for recycling to decrease economic and environmental costs
- Improve resilience: resilience of ecosystems, economy, communities, and collective preparation to disturbances, strengthen long term management of resources, opt for diversification

- Adapt to climate change and mitigate
- Opt for decreasing the environmental and economic costs

The conditions for accelerating change are under three categories complementing each other:

- Opt for co-creation and participation, through knowledge sharing and collaboration; welcoming tacit and implicit knowledge and knowledge of local communities, foster participation of multi-stakeholders at local and global scales, develop responsible governance mechanisms at local, regional, national and global scales, involve the people from producer to end-user, value the commons goods and inclusiveness
- Consider social and cultural needs, habits and traditions, human connections to the surroundings, food and nutrition security, the spiritual and material relationship with the land and environment
- Make evolve the economic model to develop fair and circular economy that reconnects producers and consumers within sustainable boundaries and give added value to solidarity

We took this framework as a backbone to specify, based on expert inputs (partners of task 4.1), what should be, for improving soil health, the specific orientations of the activities to be undertaken and the conditions under which they should be implemented (figure 1).

Figure 1. Overview of the orientations of the activities for transition for a significant impact on soil health and correspondence with the eight specific objectives and main targets identified by the Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”

To improve soil health, the changes of practices could be oriented as such,

- Regarding synergies, it should be of interest to enhance concerns in terms of ecosystem services
- Efficiency is to be linked to efficacy and to the development of prevention models
- The seek for reduction is not only in terms of resource use but also in terms of soil threats
- Concern with climate change adaptation and mitigation should be at the top of the agenda.

Regarding the way to implement such changes, providing the accurate context for change means:

- Build awareness at each level of the society, improve soil literacy.
- Co-create activities, changes of practices thanks to the engagement of the many different land users and related actors; such activities should also seek for the empowerment effect of the co-creation, collective experimentation process.
- Work under the adequate policy framework, crucial for supporting, promoting, making such changes happen; so moving with authorities, co-creating with the authorities will really improve efficiency. This goes along with a good science-policy-practice interface.
- Take into consideration the social and cultural needs, even more crucial regarding soil health since what is expected is a change of habit in many cases. This will take place locally, so being able to have a local focus is essential.
- Pay specific attention to human and social values and their translations in terms of land ownership, drivers and barriers regarding land use and soil management
- Ask for or promote efforts to develop economic models fit to circular and solidary economies are essential for the transition, it is even more crucial regarding soil health; so the actors of the value chain, the ones who are giving the sense to the economy, should be part of the co-creation process as much as possible. This, in the language of innovation, is called the 4 helix: practitioners/land users/industries, science/academics, citizens and policy makers are included.
- Combine the very local scale to the global scale, essential to change the practices and the habits to improve soil health; it should be considered in the aim of the activities but this will not be sufficient; networking activities will be essential to achieve such mixing of concerns regarding so different land uses and the extent of the scales to be combined/considered.

Our next step was to translate the aforementioned activities and ways to implement them, whatever the land use is, to significantly improve soil health (Table 2), thanks to literature analysis, and iteration with actors and stakeholders (see method).

Table 2: The ways to change practice for accelerating the sustainable transition, in terms of types of activities (right column) and conditions to implement them (left column), in bold what **deserves specific attention** for soil health and in colour, what is additional for soil health; the table is a panoramic view, it can be read as such, *“I opt to change my practice of soil management by looking for synergies of functions among ecosystems (right column), if I build the actions through a co-creation process and a specific attention to human and historical values (left column), then I can gain efficiency and efficacy”, facilitate the screening of the many variables known and the choice among them to define an improvement strategy.*

Context for implementation	Orientation of the evolution of the practices
<p><u>Develop co-creation and participation</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through knowledge sharing and collaboration: skills acquisition, intensive knowledge use and production, horizontal exchange (equal rights/sayings among the stakeholders) • Through welcoming, tacit and implicit knowledge formal, non-formal, exchange with local communities • Bring users really at the centre (testing soil practices and prototyping in LLs/LHs) • Foster participation for integration into the value and food chain, (at multilevel) of multi-stakeholders at local up to global scales: among LLs, land users, consumers, researchers, academics, ministries, big food and production chain companies, policymakers on different levels among and between LL • Foster on training and education <p><u>Bring human and social values at the centre</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity and equity: between gender, race, sexual orientation, religions; socio-economic background, multi-generational; take in consideration vulnerable people • Cultural appropriateness and history (looking back at the life of our ancestors) • Think in terms of health <p><u>Consider traditions</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As indicators of routines to have indications on how to change the. habits and break routines; • To better understand the authorities on different levels (local, regional national) • To have keys for changing the way knowledge is shared and the way people work • Infer the regional differences of activities that will be proposed or advised and the difference between people that work at discrepant levels (in terms of background, age etc.) • Improve soil literacy of the society (as most people know very few about soil and its benefits, opportunities, impacts and problems) 	<p><u>Develop synergies</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • That enhance key functions across diversified social-, trade- and eco-systems • That use the complementarities between the elements of the systems • Use landscape and urban planning and management • Work on the institutional aspects of synergies • Enhance positive interaction and complementarities between the elements of the system = regard ecosystem services for what makes sense for soil health for a certain land use, undertaken with reasonable steps (immediate multifunctional soil health for all land use is not realistic) • Open the capacity to undertake additional activities • And avoid trade-offs <p><u>Develop efficiency</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To produce the same or more, using fewer external resources: manage the resources for reduced inputs • Through efficient recycling strategies • Look for substitutions with alternate systems and practices • Stop inefficient activities <p><u>Improve resilience</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Of people, communities and ecosystems against disturbances (livelihood resilience) • Strengthen long-term management of soil to: conserve plant and animal health, biodiversity, human well-being, economic diversification and to avoid land degradation <p><u>Reduce the factors of climate change and environmental destruction</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Look for mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions • Develop the usage of cover crops, crop rotation and IPM • Lower the use of fossil fuels • Evaluate carbon sequestration and preservation • Reduced use of tillage, pesticides and fertilisers

<p><u>Develop fair and circular solidarity economy</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • That reconnects producers and consumers within sustainable boundaries • Think also in terms of opportunities for and promotion of solidarity • Look also for the livelihood for the workers and entrepreneurs (diversification of incomes, reduction of dependence on aid, community autonomy) • Evaluate the robustness of local markets, economies and employment (Fair prices, respond to local market demand, support regional value generation) • Stop certain negative activities (with or without compensations) such as profit-based decision-making excluding land-users and citizens • Think about developing certifications such as PGS: Participatory Guarantee System or CSA: Community-supported agriculture.... 	<p><u>Adapt to and mitigate climate change impacts</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Look for the adaptation of soil and surrounding system to extreme weather events such as droughts, flooding etc. • Adjust the management of knowledge) to mitigate climate change by empowering the knowledge of people being involved (including soil literacy)
--	---

2. The generic features of Living labs for soil health

Having identified the set of actions that can be undertaken, and the conditions under which their implementation will lead to significant changes, the next step was to specify what living labs can provide and infer their suitable attributes or the features that they should exhibit for being adjusted for soil health improvement.

What living labs are

Living labs are innovation arrangements built on three principles: i) co-creation, ii) with users, iii) in real life conditions. While LLs arose in the information and communication technology field, they have developed in other fields, such as city or rural development. Such characteristics make them fit for providing the conditions that might accelerate transition towards (global) sustainability goals: co-creation, considering the local culture and habits, foster innovation processes, with large set of stakeholders (citizens, industrials, policy makers, academics) consider local up to global scale. Their implementation in agroecosystems, cities, industries, brownfields, forests, natural areas is and can be more and more frequent to accelerate transitions. Living labs can be distinguished from other open-innovation arrangements, they develop specific activities in response to the three principles on which they are constituted (co-creation-with users-in real life conditions). For each sector in which they are implemented, they get unique features. Agroecosystems, cities and industrial LL can be categorised as different “place-based” LL (Mc Phee et al., 2021) and characterised by the specificities of their aim, activities, participants and context.

What is known about place-based LL is that they all operate in a real-world context, working with real communities, in real fields, in practical settings. Their aim is to engage the socioecosystem in a transition towards greater sustainability and resilience. This means working within the confines of a particular economic or socio-technical system that requires the transition. The boundaries of this system are defined by the local context. The involvement of academics in place-based LLs is a significant feature due to the breadth of knowledge required, the empowering effect expected from the co-creation process and the objective to upscale the local results. In the agroecosystems

and cities, the emphasis on multi-actor approaches, incentivized by various policies at the local, national, and international levels, has been critical to innovation for transition. Considering the origin of a LL is essential to characterise its potential to accelerate the transition process. This information helps connect the LL with regulatory frameworks, actors and policies that incentivize its emergence and helps to infer its trajectory towards agroecology transition at the systems level.

Living labs dedicated to social or societal transformation are grounded in three categories of values: business, knowledge, and social. "Knowledge" refers to the co-learning among stakeholders and partners engaged within the LLs and in their home organisations. Three key activities characterise the innovation process in LLs: co-creation, demonstration and iteration (experimentation, evaluation, and improvement). The particularity of place-based LLs is that, in addition, they emphasise environmental values in addition to business, knowledge, and social values due to their local anchorage and aim to improve resilience. They develop specific outreach and networking activities to scale out and up their achievements, particularly at the system level (value chain, landscape, territory). These LLs are also particularly knowledge-intensive and offer possibilities of transgenerational endeavours. Thanks to their local embeddedness, the co-creation process operates on a diverse and particularly heterogeneous knowledge base, including tacit and implicit knowledge. Participants in these LLs include private and public organisations, academics, users, citizens and other stakeholder (Refer to Tables 4.-6. for a specific breakdown)

Inferring the features of LL for soil health

Knowing the activities foreseen to have a significant effect on soil health (see table 2), we reconsidered the general features of place-based LL to specify what is to be added or refined for LL for healthy soils, in terms of unique aims, activities, participants and contexts, whatever the land use is.

Table 3: The table shows the characteristics of place-based Living Labs for healthy soils that are necessary and fostering the transition through the activities that will significantly influence soil health specified in Table 2. The features that all Living Labs are showing are marked in black, the ones for place-based Living Labs in red and the unique additional characteristics for health Living Labs with impact of soil health in brown.

<p>Aims</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering innovation processes • Sustainability and resilience play a major role for soil needs (that can include societal challenges) • Learning with feedback-loops and building communities that should be integrated within the process of transition • Working at multiple scales (actors, geographical, size) <p>Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development (beside 'just' testing) of strategies, including experimental innovations 	<p>Participants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the land-user as centre of attention: soil managers (farmers, advisors, allotment holders, industrials etc.), associations of organisations with interest in soil health, local administrations, local industries, citizens, academia (in and outside soil sciences) are all part of the processes and equally important • Policies and policymakers are concerned: government prominence and their link to 'mother organisations' (regional, national, international is essential) <p>Context</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real life context (not just experimental sites) • Territory, space-bound place with mixed land-use: agricultural, natural, urban, industrial
--	---

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Co-creation between all different actors and stakeholders being involved ● Iterations with feedback-loops (<i>see above</i>) as an important base for success ● Orchestration with consideration of the diversity of time frames, and long term changes ● Problematization: 'shared challenges' problems in which several/all actors are involved in problem-solving processes ● Scaling up and out: outreach and facilitation of engagement, including network dissemination, implementation of activities and adapted legislation practices ● Soil based science policy interface activities with policy makers (local to regional) are essential to include high-level decision makers ● Economic/Social/Environmental outcomes: Public and private goods, solidarity economy and development of ecosystem services to improve the overall 'well-being' of the locals and participants being involved ● Interdisciplinary systems research tackle problems from a wide range of perspectives and ideas ● Soil literacy as a major activity ● Networking activities to keep people on board and motivated to ensure the longevity of the transition process ● Sustainable funding achievements to ensure important actors are not leaving due to financial constraints 	<p>soils are all involved as different land-use types exist</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● System context for transition: system boundaries (farm, neighbourhood, value chain etc.), need to be defined clearly ● Multi-dimensional: techniques, social scales, economic scales, learning adaptivity, legislations and policies need to be considered ● Long-term set-up to ensure successful outcomes and participation of actors ● Inter/Transdisciplinary with robust scientific set-up to include variety of actors with high expertise
---	--

1. The unique features of living lab per land use

To identify the unique features of LL per land use, we imported the features published for LL in the agroecosystems, cities and industries and categorised them in terms of aims, activities, participants and context. We refined these later with the features expected for the transition for each land use to take stock of the principle, values and open-innovation dynamics that can take place in each land use, and may lead to a favourable context regarding the changes expected for soil health. We then check the features according to the generic aims, activities, participants and context expected in LL for soil health (Table 2) and add additional features for each land use. We built 4 mind maps gathering all the features of LL for one type of soil use, that were submitted to critical analysis and completion during the workshops.

▪ Agroecosystem LL

Table 4: Unique features of agroecosystem [including forestry, until we find more specific activities for forestry LL] LL foreseeing to have an impact on soil health. We departed from the features outlined of LL fit to accelerate the agroecological transition (results from the ALL-Ready Project) and infer the unique characteristics they have to demonstrate to comply with the activities foreseen to improve soil health.

Features	Any LL for the Agroecosystem LL	LL fit for accelerating AE transition	Additional concerns for soil health
Aims	The overall objective is to work towards greater sustainability and resilience of the system within which the LL operates. Innovation can take the form of new practices, business management or processes.	The option to achieve AE transition is the constant consideration of biodiversity on the site and in the surroundings. Anchoring in the "territories" is essential. The schemes have very diverse origins (from new field practices to experimental policy frameworks), as do the communities involved (farmers, policy makers, consumers, citizens, etc.). As a result, the heterogeneity and quantity of knowledge produced are particularly remarkable (from practices to policies).	The essential additional considerations is improved resilience by improved soil health <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The socioeconomic resilience of the place in which or the sector for which the LL is aiming at accelerating the transition - The sustainability and the resilience of the agri-food system, but of the resilience at the territorial, national or international level - The resilience to climate change

<p>Activities</p>	<p>The amount and level of use of data is particularly high. They are linked to the need to evaluate the performance associated with innovative proposals.</p> <p>The cyclical nature of operations is very particular, innovation cycles are seasonal and can sometimes be very long.</p> <p>Linked to external and uncontrollable factors, the level of uncertainty in experimentation and testing is high.</p> <p>The need to take local results to a larger scale, outside the strict perimeter of the living laboratory, is very important. The new practices resulting from an LL must be able to serve at least one sector.</p>	<p>The results, regardless of the location of the LL, are assessed at the system level (value chain, landscape, territory) and the transformation of the latter. The need to obtain and record data at the overall system level is very high.</p> <p>These LL are particularly knowledge-intensive, and the knowledge to be mobilised is notably heterogeneous (tacit and explicit, transgenerational).</p> <p>Given the diversity of stakeholders, it is necessary for the system to be able to avoid the information burden, to have agile governance that considers conflicts of interest, and to orchestrate co-creation.</p> <p>As the more agroecological proposals lead to more diverse products across the value chain, demonstration and iteration require a significant effort, for which experience and know-how of multi-stakeholder innovation processes are an asset.</p> <p>With regard to the knowledge produced, the role of the LL in building the capacity of the actors in the ecosystem is remarkable. It also enables the sharing of knowledge that has not yet been stabilised. These LLs must be carried out over the long term. Agroecology opens up the prospect of redesigning the production system and, because the proposals must adapt to a changing environment, brings with it an additional source of uncertainty.</p>	<p>The additional consideration relies to the peculiar heterogeneity of knowledge, actors, data to be integrated and to the extent of the time scale.</p> <p><u>Knowledge</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transgenerational knowledge acquisition and fluxes are essential - The time scale is even larger, the effects of the improvements can demand ages - Contributing to the literacy on soil for everyone is essential - Demonstration activities are of additional importance <p><u>Data</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data collection, modelling to monitor and raise awareness about soil health is also essential to the dynamics of the activities <p><u>Governance</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Due to the heterogeneity of the community engaged, the discrepant capacities to infer the impacts of soil health, the particularly long cycles between the experimentation and record of impacts, the governance of the arrangement take significant efforts and time; one activity that has to be considered as particularly determinant regarding the sustainability of the arrangement is the governance assessment.
-------------------	--	--	---

<p>Participants</p>	<p>The involvement of the public sector is particularly important. The involvement of researchers is particularly high. The role of users can be diverse and evolve over time. Due to the relatively high number and diversity of partners involved, in addition to providing scientific knowledge, the governance scheme of LLs is complex in order to maintain the involvement of various key actors in the territories and along the value chain. Researchers are also involved in designing the operation of the LL.</p>	<p>The diversity of participants is quite high. The notion of user is more diverse, it can be the advisor, the farmer, the consumer, the citizen; their role is highly evolutive, for example the farmer can be either the user of the innovation or the provider of a new practice. The opening of the system to the consumer is the major concern. The governance scheme is even more complex to maintain the commitment of the various key actors in the territories and along the value chain. Information flows are more complex and encompass more scales. Decision-making is more decentralised. These LLs produce a combination of private, public and common goods, and in the service of the common goods, which justifies more governmental and research support.</p>	<p>The precision of the types of participants to be engaged in the activity is of utmost importance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy makers and governmental organisations - Researchers and research communities of different background due to the importance of providing inter and trans disciplinary activities - Research funding organisations - Land users/managers/owners and their related organisations, and their youth associations - Private sector and industries - Service providers and consultants all over the value chain - Non-governmental organisations, including the educational, environmental and youth organisations
<p>Context</p>	<p>It is the agroecosystem that is considered. More inter- and trans-disciplinary research is used.</p>	<p>The context considered is that of climate change and food sovereignty issues, beyond the agro-ecosystem considered, put at the scale of the territory concerned. The demand to develop inter- and trans-disciplinary approaches is even stronger. Knowing the origin of the mechanisms, which traces what will have encouraged trust between stakeholders and the sharing of values, is even more essential for characterising the activity. The same is true for the regulatory framework and policies that will have prompted the emergence of the LL. This helps to monitor the trajectory</p>	<p>The boundaries to the place are essential. What makes the LL efficient regarding soil health is its concern with one of the 8 objectives of improvement of soil health specified by the Mission of the European Commission, and its place-based contribution.</p>

		of the LL and to identify the conditions for its longevity, and thus its contribution to the agro-ecological transition.	
--	--	--	--

▪ **Urban LL**

Table 5: Unique features of urban LL foreseeing to have an impact on soil health. To identify these later, we departed from the features outlined of LL fit to accelerate the resilience of urban areas and infer from the results of the SMS project the unique characteristics they have to demonstrate to comply with the activities foreseen to improve soil health

Features	Urban LL	LL fit for improving resilience	Additional concerns for soil health
Aims	<p>The overall objective is to work towards greater sustainability and resilience of the system within which the LL operates.</p> <p>The LL is place-bound, specific of an urban area</p> <p>Innovation can take the form of new practices, business management, social developments, and formal learning.</p>	<p>The option to improve the resilience of the area considered is a constant consideration, as well as its capacity to up-scale the solutions identified as soon as a positive impact is recorded.</p> <p>Anchoring in the local communities is essential, as well as the development of learning capacities and of adapted schemes to increase awareness.</p>	<p>The essential additional considerations is the interpretation of the activities to be undertaken to increase resilience</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The circularity of the production/waste management/economy/support to the citizenship - The consideration of the protection of the biodiversity as far as possible, and the greening of the city - The adaptation to climate change. <p>This goes along with activities built to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase awareness, education of climate change and living soil, the improvement of soil literacy at all levels (schools, community gardens, citizen science, urban farming....) - Consider better well-being in urban planning and real estates (spatial planning, building, redeveloping).
Activities	<p>The co-creation and iteration processes root the activities</p> <p>The considerations combine economic, environmental and social dimensions at a high level of imbrication. The outcomes are combinations of public and private goods.</p>	<p>The results have to be assessed at a more local level. The need to obtain and record quickly the achievements is very high to maintain the engagement of the various stakeholders and the local communities. .</p> <p>These LL are particularly knowledge-intensive and oriented towards raising awareness to support the changes of</p>	<p><u>Co-creation:</u></p> <p>What is more particularly at stake with the co-creation process is</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the capacity to find and create local synergies

	<p>The need to take local results to a larger scale, outside the strict perimeter of the living laboratory, is very important. The new practices resulting from an LL must be able to serve other districts or cities.</p> <p>Raising awareness is an essential pillar.</p>	<p>behaviours. All generations should be considered.</p> <p>Scaling up and out, because it is tightly in the aim of the living</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a window to analyse how people closely relate to the LL are dealing with the changes. - the alignment with the existing regulations - the creation of cross-border collaborative networks <p>The co-creation process can work as a policy instrument and offers a capacity to test new policies</p> <p>Regarding the iterations of any of the experimentations, their aim is also to record quick progress. The need is then to create a fast evaluation process.</p> <p><u>Raising awareness:</u> The first impact expected with the raising of the awareness is the changing of behaviours. The LL thus seeks to analyse, explain, follow and understand each party's drivers and barriers.</p> <p>In this respect, the LL is foreseen to out-scale the capacity to touch a large public, creating special physical zones where experiments can be carried out, evaluated, visited, raising in return awareness to a larger public.</p> <p><u>Imbrication economic-social-environmental</u></p> <p>One activity could be the establishment of an investment fund</p> <p>Because of the tight imbrication between economic, social and environmental outcomes, such LL are</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - particularly concerned with recycling and circular economies
--	---	--	--

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - able to access the latest technologies and in particular IA
Participants	<p>The involvement of citizens and their contribution to the co-creation process marks such LL, as well as the link to local policy makers. Furthermore, local industries, NGOs, academia (from various fields), local administrators, soil managers and companies should be involved.</p>	<p>These LLs produce a combination of private, public and common goods, and in the service of the common goods, which justifies more governmental and research support.</p> <p>The link with policies and policy makers is particularly stuffed and the connection with local administration is nurtured...</p>	<p>The role of all land users is of primary importance. They should all be considered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - municipalities and in these later <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o departments of soil/water/environment/green/public space o spatial and urban planning o departments linked to citizenship and public participation o the departments of economic affairs, health, safety... - Allotment holders - Business offices - Citizens <p>Regarding academia, the contribution of a variety of fields is needed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spatial planning - Natural sciences - Economic - Social sciences - Behavioural sciences regarding the public - Associations of organisations with an interest in soil health <p>What will be very specific to soil health is that although the co-creation process is undertaken with local actors, these later ensure the link with their “mother organisation”, because of the global stake of the improvement of soil health.</p>

Context	<p>It is a real-life context, day to day activities and work.</p> <p>It is place and space bound</p> <p>With always a systemic approach, what can be experimented that will be transmitted and what can be learned that can be shared.</p>	<p>Because such LL needs to have rapid outcomes, even partial, the particular context for the co-creation and iterations is within the neighbourhood and concentrated in specific areas. It should be ensured that the region or site is also ready for transition to not waste time, money and effort.</p>	<p>What makes the LL efficient regarding soil health is the complexity, in the area to work on one of the 8 objectives of improvement of soil health specified by the Mission of the European Commission.</p> <p>The scales that the LL has to consider are particularly large</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metropolitan area including peri-urban area - City boundaries - Neighbourhood - Street <p>The fields of knowledge and expertise to be combined are such that transdisciplinary is to be supported and promoted.</p>
---------	--	---	---

▪ **Industrial LL**

Table 6: Unique features of industrial LL and post-industrial (brownfield) LL foreseeing to have an impact on soil health. To identify these later, we departed from the features outlined by the SMS project regarding the activities expected to improve soil health and inferring the subjects that could be handled by industrial LL. Theoretically, industrial LLs could be separated into active industries (such as ports) and post-industrial sites (such as brownfields). For the reason to not divide everything into too many sub-categories, especially as the features for those two do not differ in a great way, we decided to keep industrial LLs as one category. Nevertheless, the slightly different features can be seen in the extended mind map built during the workshop (see annex or supplementary material).

Features	Industrial LL	Industrial LL developed regarding social and environmental responsibility of the industry	Additional concerns for soil health
Aims	<p>The overall objective is the opening out of the innovation process to resource the goods and point of views of the enterprise.</p> <p>Innovation can take the form of new networks, business management or processes and for social purposes.</p> <p>Other important aspects are soil literacy and formal learning as well as dealing with contaminants and regulations, which could be achieved through circular economy and shared sources between LLs and their stakeholders.</p>	<p>The orientation is the resilience and the consideration of the social and environmental role of the activities.</p> <p>The connection and information to neighbouring activities and organisations is an interesting option to incentivize change.</p> <p>Climate change adaptations, biodiversity protection and providing of ecosystem services are strong motivations.</p>	<p>The aims are really specific, should particularly fit with long term transformations (brownfield remediation demands decades) and deal with:</p> <p><u>The innovation purpose</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The cleaning-up of specific sites (point sources and diffuse contamination) by non-invasive, nature based and (cost-)effective remediation techniques. - Sustainable Risk-Based Site Management considering soil health as a receptor (next to ecosystem and human health) - The dealing with new / emerging contaminants and regulations - Adding value by ecosystem services to enable and improve the praxis of the (re)development and new special planning (brownfields) - The protection of natural capital because of brownfield contamination - Setting up business cases for difficult sites could even be an aim for the brownfields community to help companies/developers (earning money) and

			<p>authorities (solving problems) and the general public (better&healthy living environment)</p> <p><u>The resilience purpose</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ecosystem services: greening, biodiversity management, natural attenuation, etc - The preparation to climate change adaptation and climate resilience
Activities	<p>The need to take local results to a larger scale, outside the strict perimeter of the LL, is very important. The new practices resulting from an LL have to serve at a larger scale, at least at the level of the economic sector.</p> <p>Heterogeneity of partners, and knowledge in the involvement of co-creation is key, also for scaling up and out, which means a strong concern with the design of a purposeful management of the LL.</p>	<p>The “levels” of motivation are</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. comply with the legislation, 2. the attractiveness of the industry 3. the image of the industry 4. raising the awareness <p>With regard to the knowledge produced, the role of the LL in building the capacity of the actors in the local ecosystem is key for the transformation. It enables the sharing of knowledge that has not yet been stabilised. Because of the sharing of concerns on industrial impacts and global health, these LLs must be specifically carried out over a long term.</p>	<p>Because redevelopment of soil functions, the activities shall encompass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil and groundwater remediation - Nature based solutions - Land (brownfield) redevelopment/regeneration incl. circular land use - Sustainable Risk-Based management - Land stewardship <p>They go along with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovative approaches of monitoring impacts and effects - The design of new business models - The investment in public awareness
Participants	<p>The range of stakeholders engaged is variable according to the aim, the question of who are and will be the “user” needs to be decided.</p>	<p>These LLs produce a combination of private, public and common goods, and in the service of the common goods, which justifies more governmental and research support.</p>	<p>Participants should cover a wide range of stakeholder groups. From the general public living nearby, to advisors and service providers, to associations of organisations with interest in soil health and the heritage of the site. Altogether, the role of each land-user should be defined.</p> <p>Furthermore, the quality and role of participants might evolve over time; brownfield remediation demands decades.</p> <p>The involvement of soil managers from different origin will be particularly important;</p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From local /regional / national administration (e.g. in the case of publicly owned (post-)industrial areas or brownfields) - Owners / managers impacted by the (historic) industrial use (contamination, impacted soils) - Groups of organisations with an interest in soil health <p>The scale of the industries concerned will shape the dimension of the LL and of its impact (from local to multinational).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The link with policies and policy makers is particularly important and the connection with local administration is necessary - The academics will come from a variety of fields in and outside soils (natural sciences, economic, legal, social sciences...) - People outside of the field of soils, e.g. from natural sciences, social sciences or economics should be involved to guarantee a sustainable development of the site.
Context	<p>It is the production system and its surroundings that is considered. More inter- and trans-disciplinary research is used.</p> <p>Very important for the context, it was considered to really emphasise the real-life context including the promotion of transdisciplinarity and to keep in mind that the scales of sites can differ easily between small sites and megasites in industrial regions.</p>	<p>The context considered is that of social climate change.</p> <p>As often one important aspect is the financial context to ensure sustainability, from an environmental to a social context over a stable time frame.</p>	<p>The context is the one decided by the industry, often local, but the scale of study and of impact will vary from sites to mega sites to regions impacted by industries, and with the scale of the industry concerned; plus the specific needs of the territory in terms of soil quality and health, and of specific use, functions.</p> <p>The boundaries to the LL are essential. What makes the LL efficient regarding soil health is its concern with one or several of the 8 objectives of improvement of soil health specified by the Mission of the European Commission, and its place-based contribution.</p> <p>The specific needs of the territory in terms of soil quality and health, and of specific use, functions and are part of the context.</p>

- **Imagining LL in natural areas**

Table 7: What needs to be considered in addition to the generic activities of LL for soil health if they will be implemented in natural areas. Living Labs, and more generally the management through innovation, is not frequent in natural areas, subjected to protection or conservation approaches. How to implement actions for improving soil health is not obvious. Therefore, we needed to imagine what LL can specifically bring and what would be their unique features under such application field. We present here the result of 3 workshops of collective design. One of our first results was that there is no “one LL fits all”, they have to be scrupulously adapted to the specific area in which they are implemented, and each area add consideration and potential new attributes to the LL. The results presented in the table are not supposed to be complete, but give matter of reflexion to additionally improve what can be expected from LL for soil health.

Area	Aim	Activities	Participants	Context
Protected areas	The aim will be bounded to what needs to be specifically protected The innovation objectives and pathways will be unusual.	They might be driven by a series of case studies The searching for connecting areas, territories, countries through geographical collaboration will be high.	The composition of the participants will be totally dependent of the type of protected area concerned. Funders interested in investing in nature protection might be new comers.	It might be difficult to keep the improvement of soil health as a single goal; it will be related to other environmental concerns. On the one side, the broader picture will have to be kept in mind, on the other side, the relation to soil health will have to be nurtured.
- Mountains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The need to transform the territory to face or adapt to climate change will be prominent. - Control erosion; anticipate, model effects on on soil health, improve soil structure and cover, also regarding organic carbon - Holistic concerns: climate change, biodiversity, tourism hand in hand with soil health aims for LLs - Integrate soil preservation in natural areas into the socio-economic logic of the mountain territory (work on the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attracting political attention to mountain challenges - Imagine a common future between the different interests and overcome conflicts of use - In terms of scaling up and out, look for replications in local contexts - In terms of risk management define threshold activities in relation to exploitation - Develop activities good for soil like grazing, and for the well-being 	Additional participants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indigenous land holders (with specific right) - Not only the local in site but also the administrations of origin of the different land users (tourists) - Managers of water and waste - Actors working on natural risks - Tourism organisations - Public authorities (e.g. for funding) - Cooperation between all actors to develop 	Mountains cross over very different contexts/challenges (valley/plateau, with or without agricultural activity, ...) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities are very different according to the seasons, as well as the stakeholders - Not just focus on tourist areas

	articulation/trade-offs (land use) of activities in mountain territories. - Nature-based solutions as baseline approach	- Strong inter and transdisciplinary endeavour - Develop regulations for land management based on the cooperation between most of the actors	- regulations for land management - Promotion of wellbeing activities	
--	--	---	--	--

▪ **Initial consideration regarding LL in Forest**

Table 8: First identification of what needs to be specifically considered regarding forests. We present here the result of 3 workshops of collective design. Forest can be seen as “mixed” areas, areas with specific soil use as agricultural lands, and natural areas, in which the combination between public and private goods and concern is particularly intricated. The features mentioned in table 8 are sources of reflexion for improving the impact on soil health of LL developed in other areas than forests

Aim	Activities	Participants	Context
Strategic orientation of the activities and bring the interest of more scientific research, more diverse disciplines for such area - Foster conservation, avoid exploitation, or if necessary, focus on areas were it is less harmful to the environment, change land use if it makes sense - Increase and safeguard biodiversity within the ecosystem	Develop mediation between different interests (conservation vs. exploitation) -> sustainable combination is possible, look at the soil as an integral part - Dialogue with stakeholders and forest farmers to identify how to adress local problems and needs through sustainable approaches that consider bioeconomy and new policy directives - Test/Demonstrate/Boost (somehow) the potential of the forest for bioeconomy extension (bio-products)	Private land owners not users, and users not land owners (logging companies, hunters and rangers...)	Diversity of management, stakeholders, use... between public and private forests is to be deeply considered

Conclusions

The conceptual framework designed to infer the potential of LL and LH to improve European soil health, comprises 4 main outcomes:

- A model of change which can be seen as a common horizon whatever is the soil use, the local situation in which soil health is to be improved, the local regulation. It fits to the challenge of a pan European perspective for the 2030 achievements and orientations to act at the international level
- The identification of the generic features of LL designed for soil health, which should be found in any initiative regardless of the soil use; in addition to support the co-design activities, networking of actors and redesign of the value chains for the coherent transformation of practices, economy, regulation, public concern..., it frames the interconnectedness between LL and LH place-based in diverse areas (rural, cities, natural areas, brownfield) to meet the challenges defined for the European soil health (8 challenges of the Mission).
- The differential features of LL for soil health in areas with specific land use, agricultural lands, cities, industrial lands and brownfields. For each, specific aims, activities, types of participants and contexts were described. They are core elements helpful to design new LL or orient existing ones towards improving soil health. They help framing the orchestration between the many stakeholders and discrepant concerns, and ensure the connectedness between alike or complementary initiatives. The features are foreseen to be enriched and evolve thanks to the sharing of experience and practice among the actors.
- The potential features of LL for soil health in natural areas and forests, the latter being considered as areas of mix land use. These are initial consideration can be used to design new generations of LL, in which the combination between public and private concerns is particularly intricated and for which mitigating the impact of climate change is the major aim. As such, they could be exemplars for continuously improving the impact of LL designed for specific land use.

This framework combines scientific, political, common and practical knowledge to offer a common horizon and fertile background for local actions and initiatives that can be bound to accelerate the expected transformation. Its multi-dimensionality ensures the request of adopting holistic and open approaches for co-designing proposals. It demands to be apprehended. Our recommendation is to experiment the framework through iteration with what is locally known. Therefore we developed material for organizing workshops.

Key References

- CoreLabs (2007). Living Labs roadmap 2007-2010: recommendations on networked systems for open user-driven research, development and innovation', in Open Document, Luleå University of Technology, Centrum for Distance Spanning Technology, Luleå.
- Bergvall-Kåreborn, B. & Ståhlbröst, A. (2009) Living Lab: an open and citizen-centric approach for innovation, *Int. J. Innovation and Regional Development*, 1:4, pp.356-370.
- CIDSE. 2018. The principles of Agroecology. Towards just, resilient and sustainable food systems. Brussels.
- Declaration of the International Forum for Agroecology, Nyéléni, Mali: 27 February 2015. *Development* 58, 163–168.
- European Network of Living Labs, 2019. ENoLL Application Guidelines - 13th Wave. Available at <https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/397044439-enoll-application-guidelines-13th-wave>
- FAO. 2018. The 10 elements of Agroecology. Guiding the transition to sustainable food and agricultural systems. Rome.
- FAO. 2019. TAPE Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation 2019 – Process of development and guidelines for application. Test version. Rome.
- HLPE. 2019. Agroecological and other innovative approaches for sustainable agriculture and food systems that enhance food security and nutrition. A report by the High-Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition of the Committee on World Food Security, Rome.
- Humble, D. (2014). The Key Principles of Living Labs. Tilburg University. Available at <http://arno.uvt.nl/show.cgi?fid=133719>
- Keesstra, S. D., Bouma, J., Wallinga, J., Tiftonell, P., Smith, P., Cerdà, A., Montanarella, L., Quinton, J. N., Pachepsky, Y., van der Putten, W. H., Bardgett, R. D., Moolenaar, S., Mol, G., Jansen, B., and Fresco, L. O., (2016). The significance of soils and soil science towards realisation of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, *SOIL*, 2, 111–128, [online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-2-111-2016>
- Liedtke, C., Baedeker, C., Hasselkuß, M., Rohn, H., Grinewitschus, V. (2015): User-integrated innovation in Sustainable Living Labs: An experimental infrastructure for researching and developing sustainable product service systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 97: 106–116.
- Maring, L., G.J. Ellen., J Brils. 2022 Report on prioritisation of actor needs and criteria for Living Labs Lighthouse identification. SMS del 3.4.
- McPhee, C., Bancarz, M., Mambrini-Doudet, M., Chrétien, F., Huyghe, C., Gracia-Garza, J. 2021. The Defining Characteristics of Agroecosystem Living Labs, *Sustainability* 13(4), 1718
- Mission board on soil health and food (2020). Caring for soil is caring for life. Available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/4ebd2586-fc85-11ea-b44f-01aa75ed71a1/> [last accessed XXX]
- Nicole and Common Forum. (undated) Land stewardship: investing in the natural, social and economical capital of industrial land. Available via Nicole.org >> publications
- Schuurman, D., Mahr D., De Marez L., Ballon P., (2013). A Fourfold Typology of Living Labs: an Empirical Investigation amongst the ENoLL Community <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272566534>
- Schuurman D., De Marez, L. & Ballon, P., (2015) Living Labs: a systematic literature review
- Ståhlbröst, A. (2008). Forming future IT: the living lab way of user involvement (phD. Thesis, Luleå University of Technology). Available at <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:999816/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Steen, K., & van Bueren, E. (2017a). The Defining Characteristics of Urban Living Labs. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 7(7): 21–33. Available at: <http://timreview.ca/article/1088>

- Appendices: The Defining Characteristics of Urban Living Labs (Steen & van Bueren, 2017) Available at https://www.timreview.ca/sites/default/files/SteenVanBueren_TIMReview_July2017_AppendicesAB.pdf [last accessed at December 2020]
- Steen, K., & van Bueren, E. (2017b). Urban Living Labs A living lab way of working

Consulted websites

- CSA ALL-Ready, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000349>
- SMS project
- The Agroecology Criteria Tool. 2020. <https://www.agroecology-pool.org>
- European Network of Living Labs ENOLL: <https://enoll.org/>
- ENOLL tips and tricks for LL
 - <https://enoll.org/projects/>
 - https://enoll.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/finalcards_tt_print-1.pdf
- ENOLL membership application guideline for LL: assessment criteria
 - [hgttps://issuu.com/enoll/docs/397044439-enoll-application-guidelines-13th-wave](https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/397044439-enoll-application-guidelines-13th-wave)
- NWO call on living labs: [Living Labs in the Dutch Delta \(LLDD\) | NWO](#), [Living Labs in the Dutch Delta | NWO](#)
- Territoires d'Innovation
- The living lab initiative AAFC
- RVO website: <https://infographics.rvo.nl/livinglabs/#>